

1 **Plant-soil interactions and acclimation to temperature of**
2 **microbial-mediated soil respiration may affect predictions of**
3 **soil CO₂ efflux**

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26

27 **Abstract**

28

29 It is well known that microbial-mediated soil respiration, the major source of CO₂ from
30 terrestrial ecosystems, is sensitive to temperature. In addition, we hypothesize that some
31 mechanisms, such as acclimation of microbial respiration to temperature and/or
32 regulation by plant fresh C inputs of the temperature sensitivity of decomposition of soil
33 organic matter (SOM), should be taken into account to predict soil respiration correctly.
34 Specifically, two hypotheses were tested: 1. under warm conditions, temperature
35 sensitivity (Q_{10}) and basal rates of microbial-mediated soil respiration ($B_{S_{20}}$, respiration at
36 a given temperature) would be primarily subjected to presence/absence of plant fresh C
37 inputs; and 2. Under cold conditions, where labile C depletion occurred more slowly,
38 microbial-mediated soil respiration could adjust its optimal temperatures to colder
39 temperatures (acclimation), resulting in a net increase of respiration rates for a given
40 temperature ($B_{S_{20}}$). For this purpose, intact soil cores from an oak savanna ecosystem
41 were incubated with sufficient water supply at two contrasting temperatures (10 °C and
42 30 °C) during 140 days. To study temperature sensitivity of soil respiration, short-term
43 temperature cycles (from 5 to 40 °C at 8 hours steps) were applied periodically to the
44 soils. Our results confirmed both hypotheses. Under warm conditions ANCOVA and
45 likelihood ratio tests confirmed that both Q_{10} and $B_{S_{20}}$ decreased significantly during the
46 incubation. Further addition of glucose at the end of the incubation period increased $B_{S_{20}}$
47 and Q_{10} to initial values. The observed decrease in temperature sensitivity (Q_{10}) in
48 absence of labile C disagrees with the broadly accepted fact that temperature sensitivity
49 of the process increases as quality of the substrate decreases. Our experiment also shows
50 that after two months of incubation cold-incubated soils doubled the rates of respiration at
51 cold temperatures causing a strong increase in basal respiration rates ($B_{S_{20}}$). This suggest
52 that microbial community may have up-regulated their metabolism at cold conditions
53 (cold-acclimation), which also disagrees with most observations to date. The manuscript
54 discusses those two apparent contradictions: the decrease in temperature sensitivity in
55 absence of labile C and the increase in microbial-mediated soil respiration rates at cold
56 temperatures. While this is only a case study, the trends observed could open the
57 controversy over the validity of current soil respiration models.

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61 **Keywords:** Soil respiration, carbon cycle modeling, ecosystem ecology, climate change

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63

64 **Introduction**

65

66 How climate change will perturb the soil organic carbon (C) reservoir remains a
67 controversy. Microbial-mediated soil respiration, resulting from the decomposition of
68 soil organic matter (SOM) and its transport through the soil, ultimately contributes to an
69 important portion of soil CO₂ efflux (Hanson et al. 2000; Bond-Lamberty et al. 2004;
70 Tang and Baldocchi 2005; Hahn et al. 2006). This fact highlights the need to understand
71 physiological mechanisms of microbial metabolism. Biologists have long used
72 exponential functions to describe the temperature dependence of soil respiration, a
73 concept originated in the 19th century physical-chemistry models of Arrhenius (1889) and
74 Van't Hoff (1896). Current models predict that global warming will increase the net CO₂
75 emissions from terrestrial ecosystems due to the strong sensitivity of heterotrophic
76 respiration to temperature (Cox et al.; 2000; Friedlingstein et al.; 2003, Rustad et al.
77 2001). However, those models also highlight the large uncertainties associated to
78 predicted soil emissions component (Cox et al. 2000, Cramer et al. 2001, Meir et al.
79 2006) which are primarily due to the limited, but growing, knowledge of the mechanisms
80 underlying soil respiration (Davidson and Janssens 2006; Davidson et al. 2006).

81

82 One of these mechanisms is acclimation, which is the homeostatic adjustment of
83 respiration rates in organisms to compensate for a change in temperature (Atkin et al.
84 2000). We know that plants can adjust physiologically, by increasing their metabolic
85 activity at low temperatures and/or down-regulating their metabolic activity at warm
86 conditions (Berry & Bjorkman 1980; Atkin and Tjoelker 2003). Concerning soils, it is not
87 yet clear whether microbial-mediated soil respiration acclimates to climatic changes and
88 how this acclimation would affect future predictions of terrestrial CO₂ emissions. Recent
89 studies have criticized first order kinetics models because they do not reflect the capacity
90 of microbial communities to functionally acclimate to previously unknown environmental
91 conditions (Schimel 1995; Stark and Firestone 1996; Schimel and Gullledge 1998; Balser
92 et al. 2001; Hawkes et al. 2005), as has been shown in a number of studies (Zogg et al.
93 1997; Balser and Firestone 2004; Waldrop and Firestone 2006).

94

95 At the ecosystem level, several studies have observed a decrease in soil respiration in
96 association with metabolic down-regulation at warmer temperatures (Luo et al. 2001;
97 Stromgren and Linder 2002; Giardina and Ryan 2000; Misson et al. 2007). However a
98 number of studies have attributed this apparent acclimation to other factors; as
99 temperature increases the imbalance arises between the supply (photosynthesis) and the
100 utilization (respiration) of the most labile C fraction, product of plant activity (Rustad et
101 al. 2001; Kirschbaum 1995; 2004; Gu et al. 2004; Eliasson et al. 2005; Davidson et al.
102 2006; Hartley et al. 2007). Recently synthesized sugars contribute substantially to soil
103 respiration (Hogberg et al. 2001; Tang et al. 2005) and provide microbes with the energy
104 to support decomposition of SOM (priming) (Kuzyakov and Cheng 2001; 2004; Fontaine
105 et al. 2003;2007). Moreover, because our perception of temperature sensitivity of
106 decomposition could be strongly affected by substrate supply at the enzymatic-process
107 level (Davidson and Janssens 2006), it is important to distinguish apparent (observed)
108 from intrinsic (real) temperature sensitivity of soil respiration.

109

110

111 Following these open controversies, we hypothesize that factors not taken into account by
112 current models, such as thermal acclimation of microbial-mediated soil respiration and/or
113 the size of the labile fraction of soil organic matter (SOM) at a given time, may strongly
114 affect soil respiration and its response to temperature. Specifically, we here hypothesize
115 that 1. Under warm conditions Q_{10} (the increase in respiration for every 10 °C) and B_{s20}
116 (The basal respiration rate for a given temperature) of microbial-mediated soil respiration
117 will be subjected to modulations by plant fresh C inputs, i.e. the lack of plant fresh C
118 inputs will affect respiration and its response to temperature negatively; and 2. Under
119 cold conditions and more slowly depletion of labile C, soil respiration will increase at
120 lower temperatures with time (acclimation), affecting also Q_{10} and the B_{s20} , i.e. as
121 observed in plants, microbial community may adjust their metabolism to new
122 temperatures. For this aim, soils were incubated at two contrasting temperatures, above
123 and below the mean annual temperature, respectively, for 140 days. To investigate
124 possible patterns of acclimation to temperature during the incubation short-term
125 temperature changes were applied periodically to the same soils.

126

127 **Materials and Methods**

128

129 **Site description**

130

131 Intact soils cores were sampled from an oak savanna field site (Tonzi Ranch), located at
132 38.4311° N, 120.966° W near Ione, Ca. The altitude of the site is 177 m and the terrain is
133 relatively flat. The woodland overstory consists of scattered blue oak trees (*Quercus*
134 *douglasii*). Also registered in the site survey were occasional grey pine trees (*Pinus*
135 *sabiniana*). The understory landscape has been managed, as the local rancher has
136 removed brush and the cattle graze the grass and herbs. The understory consists of
137 exotic annual grasses and herbs; the species include *Brachypodium distachyon*,
138 *Hypochaeris glabra*, *Bromus madritensis*, and *Cynosurus echinatus*. Deciduous blue oaks
139 (*Quercus douglasii*) dominate the savanna site with 144 stem per hectare in a 200 by 200
140 m sampling plot. Their average height is 9.41 ± 4.33 m, and their mean basal area is
141 0.074 ± 0.0869 m² (Chen et al. 2006). The mean annual temperature is 16.3°C, and 559
142 mm of precipitation fall per year, as determined from over 30 years of data from a nearby
143 weather station at Ione, California.

144

145 **Experimental design**

146

147 We decided to sample at peak of biomass and photosynthetic activity (Xu and Baldocchi
148 2003) when soil metabolic activity is typically at its highest values (Tang and Baldocchi
149 2005, Curiel Yuste et al. 2007). Intact soil cores were collected on 15 April 2006. By this
150 date, grasses were growing and tree leaves just came out, and mean soil temperature was
151 approx. 15 °C. Thirty undisturbed soil cores of 80 cm³ (4 x 4 x 5 cm) were collected from
152 the upper part of the soil profile (0-5 cm) with a soil sampler containing a stainless-steel
153 cylinder within. Soil cores were kept in their stainless steel container to maintain the bulk
154 density and known volume (80 cm³).

155

156 Soil cores were collected at 10 sub-locations, 5 sub-locations randomly chosen in the
157 proximity of a tree (blue oak) and the other 5 in sub-locations randomly chosen at least
158 20 m away from the nearest tree. We did not find important differences in the respiration
159 and its response to temperature (Q_{10}) of soils collected in open and under tree areas (data
160 not shown). Therefore, data from both areas were pooled together. Within each sub-
161 location, 3 pseudo-replicates were taken carefully one next to each-other to avoid large
162 'environmental' differences (e.g. plant cover, texture) among them. From these soil cores,
163 one was used for incubation at 10 °C (to test 'cold-acclimation'), one was used for
164 incubation at 30 °C (to test 'warm-acclimation') and the last one was used for analysis
165 (soil water content, soil water potential, total carbon and nitrogen). Therefore, from a
166 total number of 30 cores, ten cores were maintained at 30 °C, other ten were maintained
167 at 10 °C and the last ten soil cores were used for laboratory analytical studies. Given the
168 number of replicates (ten per treatment), and the methodology used, we can assume that
169 soil cores at cold and warm treatments held the same biogeochemical properties, at the
170 initiation of the incubation treatment.

171
172 Because the mean annual temperature ($\overline{T_a}$) of the ecosystem is around 16 °C we used
173 these two contrasting temperatures to bound the climatic average. At the time of sample
174 collection, soils were sufficiently moist (Table 1). To avoid water limitations during the
175 incubation period, soil cores were placed within 473 ml glass Mason jars equipped with a
176 continuously water-saturated sponge to keep the soil moistened by capillary action. By
177 continuously maintaining the sponge water-saturated soil moisture was maintained near
178 field capacity during the incubation.

179
180 To assess the temperature sensitivity of soil decomposition at different stages of the
181 incubation, four temperature cycles were performed. During a cycle, temperatures were
182 increased from 5 to 40 °C and then decreased again to 5 °C at temperature steps of 5, 20,
183 30 and 40 °C. To ensure temperature equilibration within the soil cores, soil CO₂ efflux
184 was measured after approximately 6-7 hours exposure to the new temperature. To ensure
185 the reliability of the measurements, soil CO₂ efflux was measured two consecutive times
186 at each soil sample and an average of the two measurements was used for later
187 calculations. Therefore, each temperature cycle lasted approximately 36-42 hours. These
188 cycles were performed at 10, 17, 61 and 140 days after the incubation started.

189
190 To test the first hypothesis, glucose - a source of labile C - was added to soils depleted of
191 labile C (warm incubated during 140 days). At the end of the incubation period (day 140),
192 five of the soils previously incubated at 30 °C received 1 ml of a glucose solution (100mg
193 ml⁻¹). To ensure that the glucose pool did not become exhausted during the temperature
194 perturbation cycle, the quantity added was based on the amount of CO₂ depleted during
195 the first temperature cycle. The glucose was injected using a syringe in several locations
196 within the cores to spread the glucose evenly. Two temperature cycles, as described
197 above, were performed before ((-) glucose) and after ((+) glucose) the addition of the
198 solution.

199
200

201 **Soil analyses**

202

203 Bulk density, soil moisture as well as soil carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) concentrations
204 were measured at time 0 using the soil cores spared for analysis. Soil moisture was
205 estimated gravimetrically, by drying the samples during 48 hours at 75 °C. By estimating
206 the dry weight of the soil cores of known volume (80 cm³) we estimated the bulk density
207 of the sample. Results of moisture and C content of those soil cores were used to
208 calculate the soil moisture and C content of the incubated soils assuming that the
209 proportion (g/g) of water and C were similar for both sets of soils. For more information
210 about soil analyses and methods see Curiel Yuste et al. (2007). Results are presented in
211 Table 1.

212

213

214 **Calculation of respiration rates**

215

216 We measured soil CO₂ efflux using a dynamic flow-through system which operated
217 under closed and non-steady state conditions. Concentrations of CO₂ in the system were
218 measured with a Li-Cor 6262 infrared gas analyzer (Li-Cor, Lincoln, NE). For more
219 information about the system, see Curiel Yuste et al. (2007). Soil respiration was
220 calculated from the linear increase of CO₂ concentration within the system with time
221 (normally 40 second time interval) (Livingston GP & Hutchinson GL 1995; Curiel Yuste
222 et al. 2007):

223

224
$$F_a = \frac{(\Delta CO_2 - a) \times V_s}{t \times A} \quad (1)$$

225

226 where F_a is the total soil CO₂ evolved from the soil sample during the sampling interval
227 ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), ΔCO_2 is the change in CO₂ concentration ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$) within the system
228 during the sampling interval, t is the sample interval (s), a is the intercept of the linear
229 function of the relationship between CO₂ concentration and time, V_s is the volume of the
230 system (l) and A is the area of the upper part of the core ($1.81 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$). Volume of the
231 system (V_s) was estimated as 0.57 l (Curiel Yuste et al. 2007).

232

233 **Sensitivity to temperature of soil CO₂ efflux**

234

235 To assess the sensitivity to temperature of respiration, we used the Q_{10} function. Q_{10}
236 represents the factor by which respiration is multiplied when temperature increases by 10
237 °C:

238

239
$$F_a = B_{s_{20}} Q_{10}^{\frac{T-20}{10}} \quad (2)$$

240

241 Where F_a is the measured soil CO₂ efflux on area basis ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), $B_{s_{20}}$ is the basal
242 respiration rate at 20 °C and T is the temperature of soil at measurement time. The basal
243 respiration rate was evaluated at 20 °C, a temperature in between both treatments. We
244 fitted this exponential function at each temperature cycle for each soil core individually

245 (warm- and cold-acclimated soil cores) and for the whole temperature range between 5
246 and 40 °C.

247

248 **Calculation of soil carbon pools**

249

250 There are several equations that can be used to infer the labile and recalcitrant C pools in
251 soils. In principle, these are based on the changes in the slope of the C mineralization
252 along the incubation period (Sleutel et al. 2005; Kätterer et al. 1998; Townsend et al.
253 1997). The method used in this study assumes that the C mineralized initially had a fast
254 turnover and is labile (fast pool), while the remaining fraction has a slow turnover and is
255 recalcitrant (slow pool) (Townsend et al. 1997). We used a two pool first-order kinetics
256 model used in prior works (Breland 1994; Franzluebbers et al. 1994; Bernal et al. 1998):

257

$$258 \quad C_{cum}(t) = C_f [1 - e^{-(k_f t)}] + (C_{total} - C_f) [1 - e^{-(k_s t)}] \quad (3)$$

259

260 In *equation 3* $C_{cum}(t)$ is the cumulative mineralized C at a certain time of the incubation,
261 expressed as F_a (gC m⁻²), k_f and k_s are the decomposition rate of the fast and slow C pool
262 (d⁻¹), C_f is the carbon content of the fast pool and C_{total} the calculated soil C (Table 2) (Kg
263 C m⁻²). C_{cum} was calculated for each day using linear interpolation between days where
264 soil respiration was measured. This model gave the best fits out of the three different
265 kinetics models compared in Curiel Yuste et al. (2007). The fit was improved by
266 constraining the size of the slow pool (assumed C_s as $C_{total}-C_f$) (McLauchlan & Hobbie
267 2004). It should be pointed out that the ‘slow pool’ in this study refers to a mixture of soil
268 C pools of very different turnover times, probably from weeks up to centuries or
269 millennia (Trumbore 2000).

270

271 We wanted to test whether the differences in respiration rates of cold- and warm-
272 incubated soils could be explained by differences in temperature. To this end we modeled
273 temporal evolution of soil respiration based on observed temporal evolution of soil
274 respiration and temperature sensitivity. Soil respiration in cold-incubated soils did not
275 follow an exponential decay shape (Figure 1), and therefore the fits and coefficients
276 generated by *equation 3*, when fitted to cold-incubated respiration rates, were not
277 meaningful (data not shown). We, therefore, assumed that: 1. Initial values of labile C
278 (C_f) in cold-incubated soils were the same as in warm-incubated soils; 2. Decomposition
279 rate were sensitive to temperature with sensitivity equal to a Q_{10} of 2 (standard value of
280 Q_{10}). We therefore used the decomposition rate (k_f and k_s) obtained from fitting warm-
281 incubated soil cores (*equation 3*) and a Q_{10} function (similar to *equation 2*) to model the
282 decomposition rate of labile and recalcitrant pools of the cold incubated soil cores:.

283

$$284 \quad k_{wi30} = k_{ci10} Q_{10}^{\frac{T-10}{10}} \quad (4)$$

285

286 Where k_{wi30} is the decomposition rate of either the fast (i=f) or the slow (i=s) C pools
287 obtained from the fit of *equation 3* to respiration rates of warm-incubated soils (at 30 °C),
288 k_{ci10} is the basal decomposition rate at a temperature of 10 °C, which coincided with cold-
289 incubation temperature. This basal decomposition rate was therefore used as the

290 decomposition rate of the fast (i=f) or the slow (i=s) C pools for the cold-incubated soils.
291 The value of Q_{10} was fixed at 2 and the value of T was 30.

292

293

294 **Statistical Analyses**

295 Analysis of co-variance was used to test significant differences in B_{s20} and Q_{10} between
296 and within both temperature treatments (i.e. warm 30°C and cold 10°C). We carried out a
297 null model likelihood ratio test for the significance of Q_{10} 's. We specifically tested the
298 null hypotheses of no change in Q_{10} during the incubation ($H_0 = dQ_{10} = 0$). For each
299 treatment (warm or cold), the null model was fitted with all of available samples, and a
300 sub-model was also fitted for each incubation time. A χ^2 value was calculated with the
301 logarithmic likelihood from the null model and the logarithmic likelihood from the model
302 fitted at each incubation time. This statistic has an asymptotic χ^2 -distribution with $q-1$
303 degrees of freedom, where q is the effective number of covariance parameters (those not
304 estimated to be on a boundary constraint). If the probability $>\chi^2$ is less than 0.05, the null
305 model is rejected. In other words, differences in parameters of the models fitted by
306 incubation time are significant. Likelihood ratio test was performed by using the MIXED
307 procedure of the standard statistical software package SAS (Version 9.1, SAS Institute
308 Inc., Cary, NC, USA). Analysis of co-variance in STATISTICA, and were tested against
309 a significance level of 0.05.

310

311 Results

312

313 No biochemical differences between both warm and cold incubated cores were found at
314 the beginning of the incubation (Table 1). Despite the similar initial substrate quantity
315 and quality of both sets of soils (Table 1) respiration rates differed significantly between
316 temperature treatments (10°C or 30°C) (Figure 1). Initial respiration rates of the warm-
317 incubated soil cores were almost five times higher than those of the cold-incubated soil
318 cores (Figure 1a). Soil respiration decreased exponentially under warm conditions during
319 the incubation period (Figure 1a). Under warm temperatures respiration was highest
320 when remaining C_f was highest (Figure 1a and 1b). Simulated depletion of labile C,
321 calculated from the coefficients obtained from *equation 3* (warm incubations) and
322 *equation 3 and 4* (cold incubations) also indicates that labile C pool was probably
323 depleted faster in warm soils (Figure 1b). This is because k_f , the decomposition rate of
324 this fast C pool, was much higher for warm than for cold-incubated soils (Table 1).

325

326 Evolution of respiration rates under warm conditions were well explained by an
327 exponential function (Figure 2a). Under cold-conditions initial respiration rates were well
328 explained by the decomposition rate obtained from warm incubated soils (k_{wf} and k_{ws} ,
329 respectively) and corrected for temperature (*equation 4*) (Figure 2b). After two months of
330 incubation, however, respiration rates at 10 °C increased and were best explained by
331 applying the k coefficients obtained under warm-incubations (k_{wf} and k_{ws}) (dotted line
332 Figure 2b).

333

334 Study of the short-term temperature response of microbial-mediated respiration rates
335 indicates a general decrease in basal respiration rates (B_{s20}) and the sensitivity to
336 temperature (Q_{10}) with time (Table 2 and Figure 3). Likelihood ratio test of comparing
337 the Q_{10} constant vs the Q_{10} varying model was statistically significant for both the warm
338 and the cold treatment (data not shown), which confirmed the results obtained in Table 2.
339 Ancova analyses with “treatment” (cold-warm) and “time” as independent variables
340 indicated strong relation between “treatment” and B_{s20} (B_{s20} was significantly higher in
341 cold than in warm-incubated soils) and between “time” and Q_{10} (Q_{10} decreased
342 significantly with time). Within treatment, there was a strong effect of time over both
343 B_{s20} and Q_{10} (Table 2). B_{s20} increased significantly in the cold treatment (95%
344 confidence interval) while in the warm treatment B_{s20} decreased significantly (p value <
345 0.0001). Intercept of the linear fit between “time” and B_{s20} and Q_{10} coefficients further
346 shows that temperature sensitivity (Q_{10}) at the beginning of the incubation were equal
347 (1.9) for both set of soils, but B_{s20} was more than double in the warm- than in the cold-
348 incubated set of soils. The Q_{10} coefficient decreased significantly with time at both
349 treatments (slope of the linear fit between “time” and Q_{10} significantly different from 0),
350 at a 95% confidence interval (Table 2). The decrease was more pronounced under cold-
351 than under warm incubated soils (Table 2) but as said above, likelihood ratio test
352 confirmed that the decrease was statistically significant for both the warm and the cold
353 treatment.

354

355 Glucose, the most common plant exudate (Grayston et al. 1996), was added to C_f -
356 depleted soils (incubated during 140 days at 30 °C) to study the effect in soil respiration
357 and its sensitivity to temperature (Figure 4). Addition of this energy-rich, nutrient-poor
358 substrate caused a significant increase on B_{s20} and Q_{10} to values similar to initial ones
359 (compare Figure 3a to Figure 4).

360

361 Discussion

362

363 In the studied soils, values of the easily decomposable pool (C_f) (Table 1) were in the
364 higher range of that observed in Rey and Jarvis (2006). This easily decomposable pool
365 has been correlated to plant activity (Curiel Yuste et al. 2007), which was at its peak
366 during the sampling date (see Materials and Methods section). Active plants are
367 continuously releasing organic material to soil in the form of easily decomposable
368 substrate (exudates) such as simple sugars, amino acids and organic acids (Lynch and
369 Whipps 1990, Grayston et al. 1996, Gleixner et al. 2005, Norton and Firestone 1991). It is
370 therefore likely that the relatively large size of labile C pool in the studied soils could be
371 partially attributed to the peak in plant activity at the sampling time.

372

373 Microbial-mediated soil respiration occurred faster at higher temperatures (Figure 1a), as
374 it has been shown in multiple experiments (e.g. Reichstein et al. 2000, Dalias et al. 2001).
375 Under warm conditions, microbial-mediated respiration rates decreased exponentially in
376 a very predictable way (Figure 1a, 2a). Temporal evolution of microbial-mediated soil
377 respiration could therefore be explained by first order kinetics: respiration was
378 proportional to the amount of a discrete number of C pools (two in the study case) and the
379 decomposition rate of each C pool, which was temperature dependent (Figure 2, Table 1).
380 Respiration rates for a given temperature decreased gradually under the warm conditions
381 of the incubation (Table 2, Figure 3), which was reflected in decrease in temperature
382 sensitivity (Q_{10}) and basal respiration rates (B_{s20}) of warm incubated soils (Figure 3). At
383 the end of the incubation, both Q_{10} and B_{s20} were significantly lower than at the
384 beginning of the incubation (Table 2). It is a well known fact that respiration rates for a
385 given temperature decreases as labile C fraction also decreases. However, the decrease in
386 Q_{10} in absence or shortage of labile C disagrees with theory (e.g. Bosatta and Agren
387 1998), which states that temperature sensitivity of respiration should increase as the
388 quality of SOM decreases. The increase in B_{s20} and Q_{10} to values closer to initial values
389 after addition of glucose -the most common plant exudates (Grayston et al. 1996) -
390 (compare Figure 3a to Figure 4) further confirms the idea of higher Q_{10} in presence of
391 labile C.

392

393 A number of observational 'deviations' from the kinetic theory (Liski et al. 1999, Luo et
394 al 2001, Giardina and Ryan 2003, Strömberg and Linder 2002, Fang et al. 2005) suggest,
395 however, that the complexity of the process transcend a single theory (Davidson and
396 Janssens 2006). Physical or biochemical accessibility to substrate by soil enzymes
397 (Davidson et al. 2006, Davidson & Janssens 2006) may strongly affect the response to
398 temperature of microbial decomposition of SOM and obscure the intrinsic temperature
399 sensitivity of less labile fractions of SOM. Under the laboratory conditions of this
400 experiment and after 4 months of incubation, the negative effect on Q_{10} caused by

401 depletion of labile C and subsequent limitation in substrate accessibility to microbes and
402 exo-enzymes was probably stronger than the positive effect on Q_{10} derived from
403 decomposition of more recalcitrant SOM. Therefore we conclude that in natural
404 ecosystems temperature sensitivity of microbial-mediated soil respiration would be
405 primarily subjected to changes in the accessibility to an easily decomposable C pool
406 rather than to changes in the intrinsic temperature sensitivity of the C pool being
407 decomposed.

408
409 On the other hand, the increase in $B_{S_{20}}$ and the decrease in Q_{10} after 60 days exposure to
410 cold (Figure 1a, Figure 3d) were unexpectedly pronounced. Substrate depletion probably
411 occurred more slowly in these soils, as suggested by simulated depletion of labile C
412 (Figure 1b). The fairly constant $B_{S_{20}}$ before day 60 and the increase in $B_{S_{20}}$ after day 60
413 furthermore support this fact. The increase in $B_{S_{20}}$ and the decrease in Q_{10} after two
414 months of incubations were mainly caused by a strong increase in respiration rates at
415 colder temperatures (Figure 3) which could not be explained by a first-order kinetic
416 model corrected for temperature (Figure 2b). It must be pointed out that soils in this
417 ecosystem rarely experienced cold temperatures. Average temperature at 2 cm depth in
418 the mineral soil, 7 days prior to sample collection, was 15 °C. Mean annual temperature
419 at this depth of soil profile was 19 °C and temperatures similar to those of the incubation
420 (10 °C) were only reached during the first month of 2005 (approximately 2 months and a
421 half before sampling). It is well known that microbes may experience physiological
422 changes to become tolerant to cold conditions, e.g. maintenance of membrane fluidity or
423 synthesis of cold-tolerant enzymes (Margesin et al. 2007). Moreover, microbial
424 community structure changes under contrasting temperatures regimes, favoring microbes
425 better adapted to the new temperatures (Zogg et al. 1997; Pettersson and Bååth 2003;
426 Waldrop and Firestone 2004; 2006). Therefore it is possible that soil microbial
427 community under cold conditions may have developed mechanisms of acclimation to
428 these sub-optimal temperatures (cold-acclimation).

429
430 However, this observed transient doubling of respiration rates is just a singularity that
431 disagrees with most of the laboratory observations at low temperatures reported to date
432 (Reichstein et al. 2000; Dalias et al. 2001; Rey et al. 2006). We nonetheless contend that
433 the response observed in this study cannot be fully compared with previous observations
434 where initial physical and biological conditions of soil were strongly modified by soil
435 mixing, sieving, rewetting and/or oven drying. Manipulations such as sieving breaks up
436 aggregates and makes available previously protected SOM, which increase initial
437 respiration rates, with respect to intact cores (Hartley et al. 2007). Strong changes in soil
438 water content (oven drying and rewetting) also affect microbial community composition
439 (Lipson et al. 2002; Fierer et al. 2003), probably favoring opportunistic species over the
440 endemic community (Allison 2005). This therefore suggests that other experiments
441 should be similarly designed to refute/support our results.

442
443 Our experimental design therefore shows that: 1. under warm conditions, fast depletion of
444 an easily accessible C pool affected negatively to both microbial-mediated soil respiration
445 and its temperature sensitivity; and 2. Microbial community, in this experiment, respired
446 more for a given temperature with time (cold-acclimation). Our results open the

447 controversy of whether soil respiration in a changing climate could be satisfactorily
448 explained using simple first-order kinetics and fixed values of temperature sensitivity of
449 soil respiration.

450

451 **Conceptual remarks**

452

453 Based on our results, Figure 5 illustrates an example of how our perception of microbial-
454 mediated soil respiration at a temperature reference ($B_{S_{Tref}}$) and its temperature
455 sensitivity (Q_{10}) could be affected by environmental factors.

456

457 Under no water limitations, the temperature response curve of soil respiration would be
458 primarily controlled by presence/absence of labile C carbon (Figure 5a), which in natural
459 ecosystems is provided by plants. This will affect the perception of $B_{S_{Tref}}$ and Q_{10} on a
460 fixed temperature range. Contrary to theory, this suggests that the negative effect on Q_{10}
461 caused by depletion of an easily accessible C pool was probably stronger than the
462 positive effect on Q_{10} derived from decomposition of more recalcitrant SOM. For the
463 purpose of this study, these results suggest that models should take into account the effect
464 of plant-derived fresh C inputs to correctly understand temperature sensitivity of soil
465 respiration.

466

467 When limitations in fresh labile C were not an issue, which was the case in the cold-
468 incubated soils, microbial communities could increase their respiration rates at low
469 temperatures (Figure 5b). These adjustments resulted in strong changes in $B_{S_{Tref}}$ and Q_{10}
470 for a given temperature range. While current models allocate fixed Q_{10} 's and
471 decomposition rate for a given SOM pool, we here show that microbial acclimation to
472 cold temperatures may affect both, respiration rates for a given temperature and Q_{10} for a
473 given temperature range. Future predictions of soil CO_2 efflux can thus not be
474 satisfactorily predicted if we do not understand patterns of microbial community
475 acclimation to changing temperatures.

476

477

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479

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734

735 **Table 1** Physical and biochemical properties of the oak savanna soil under study for
 736 warm (warm) and cold (cold) incubated soil cores. C_f =fast C fraction of soil C; k_f =
 737 decomposition rate of fast C fraction and k_s = decomposition rate of slow C fraction, both
 738 calculated with *equation 3* (only meaningful coefficients obtained with warm incubated soils are
 739 presented). Numbers in bracket correspond to the standard deviation.
 740
 741

	warm	cold
dry weight (g)	132(12)	131(11)
Soil moisture (g/g)	33.5 (5.8)	33.8 (5.7)
N content (g)	0.25(0.10)	0.25(0.05)
C content (g)	2.7(0.8)	2.7(0.7)
bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.5(0.1)	1.4(0.1)
C_f (g)	0.14(0.04)	-
k_f (d ⁻¹)	0.05 (0.03)	-
k_s (d ⁻¹)	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ ($1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	-

	Treatment vs time						Time effect at each treatment							
	Time		Treatment		Intercept		Cold treatment				Warm treatment			
	Beta	p-value	Beta	p-value	value	p-value	Slope	p-value	Intercept	p-value	Slope	p-value	Intercept	p-value
Q₁₀	-0.027	0.002	-0.006	0.520119	0.3	0.000000	-0.04	0.010	0.30	>0.001	-0.02	0.050	0.26	>0.001
BS₂₀	-0.025	0.400	0.072	0.031515	0.4	0.000027	0.05	0.140	0.24	0.012	-0.10	0.030	0.48	>0.001

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Table 2. Left panels: Results of analysis of covariance with a dependent variable (Q₁₀ or BS₂₀), and independent categorical variable (treatment= cold or warm) and a continuous independent variable (Time = 1 to 4). Right panels: Results of the effect of time on coefficients (Q₁₀ or BS₂₀) generated by each treatment (cold and warm).

747 **Figure captions**

748

749 **Figure 1.** (a) Microbial-mediated soil respiration for two different incubation
750 temperatures, warm and cold, as a function of time. Error bars represent the standard
751 error of the mean; (b) Modeled available labile C fraction for the warm and the cold
752 treatment of the study.

753

754 **Figure 2.** (a) Modeled and measured microbial-mediated soil respiration for warm
755 incubated soil cores as a function of time; (b) Modeled and measured microbial
756 respiration for cold incubated soil cores as a function of time. Symbols represent
757 observed respiration rates. Solid line in Figure 2a represents modeled rates of soil
758 respiration using *equation 3*. Solid line in Figure 2b represents modeled rates of soil
759 respiration of cold-incubated soils, using the k values obtained for warm soils (*equation*
760 *3*) corrected for temperature (*equation 4*). Dotted line of Figure 2b represents the results
761 of modeling cold incubation respiration rates using the warm incubated k values, not
762 corrected by temperature. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean

763

764 **Figure 3.** Short term temperature response curves of microbial-mediated soil respiration
765 rates at warm and cold-incubated soils at different days after incubation began 10 (a), 17
766 (b), 60 (c) and 140 days (d). Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. All p-
767 values obtained from the regressions were below the 0.005 significant level.

768

769 **Figure 4.** Short term temperature response curves of microbial-mediated soil respiration
770 rates of warm-incubated soils before ((-) Glucose) and after ((+) Glucose) addition of
771 glucose solution. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Q₁₀ values and
772 standard error of the fit (parenthesis) are also provided.

773

774 **Figure 5.** Illustrative scheme of how the studied factors may affect Q₁₀ and B_{STref} for a
775 given range of temperatures; The Figures represent a hypothetical temperature response
776 curve for a given enzyme-driven process (which in the studied case was microbial-
777 mediated soil respiration) on time 1 (initial conditions) and time 2 (final conditions).
778 Solid lines represent the typical exponential curves used to represent temperature
779 sensitivity of respiration. Curves were enclosed between two temperatures, one cold and
780 one warm, represented by open circles. Text on the right side of the panels represents the
781 trends of Q₁₀ and B_{STref} from time 1 to time 2. Negative means net decrease and positive
782 net increase of the coefficients (Q₁₀ and B_{STref}) from time 1 to time 2, respectively. Figure
783 a) represents the effect of incubation time and warming over Q₁₀ and B_{STref}. Figure b)
784 represents the effect of incubation time and cold-temperatures over Q₁₀ and B_{STref}.

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788 **Figure 1**
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791 **Figure 2**
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798 **Figure 3**

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803 **Figure 4**
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807 **Figure 5**
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